

Shackles of Tyranny

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Annotation:

The content of this article is devoted to the mass extermination of the population of Uzbekistan by the USSR in the 20th century. The merciless execution and expulsion of independent people. Although such atrocities were committed, they could not destroy the feeling of independence of the people. Cruel human aggression. He will stop at nothing to destroy the feeling of an independent state in people. In the article you can learn about the crimes and punishment of those who committed the repressions. The opinions expressed about the court and prison life are based on the literature used.

Keywords: 20th century, mass repressions, "blank spots", "Counter-revolutionary crimes", the label "enemy of the people", socially alien elements.

It is very important for everyone to know their history. After all, for you and for us, it is both an obligation and a duty. We will introduce you to another page of history.

It is no exaggeration to say that the 20th century was a period of suffering, tragedy and great colonialism for all of humanity. It must be admitted that there were many innovations during this period, but humanity faced great difficulties. For this reason, we must study every page of history.

It was during this time that the Soviet state inflicted great moral and material damage on the people of Uzbekistan. Their attitude towards the Uzbeks was unfounded and cruel. Some say that there is

no need to look for the past and that the events that took place should be forgotten because they are in the past. It is simply not in our nature to forget about it. It is always necessary to learn from history, analyze good examples and analyze bad ones

Our first president Islam Karimov on the threshold of independence, in June 1990 at the congress of the Republican Party, in his lecture "Studying the past, with confidence in the future" spoke about the main lessons of the past and said: "Unreasonable mass repressions, collectivization and increasingly more terrible examples appear, showing that during the period of industrialization, the basic principles of life were mercilessly destroyed, the spiritual values and traditions of the people were forged, some people were sold for money, and people who found themselves in the midst of a socio-economic crisis, neglected the most basic needs and vital requirements of people, "remains clear." [1;165]

"We are for the complete elimination of "blank spots", be it the press movement, collectivization, repression, violations associated with stagnation. ... to condemn our past from head to toe would be an unforgivable mistake before the memory of our ancestors, before our children and grandchildren" [1;166])

During the period of reconstruction, there is information about the number of victims of repression in the USSR based on different methodical calculations at different times. In order to understand the essence of political repression, its scale and tragedy, it is necessary to carefully study the Article 58 of the Criminal Code of the USSR and the Allied Republics, entitled "State Crimes" ("Государственные преступления") also emerges.

Paragraph 1 of that Article 58 is called "Counter-Revolutionary Crimes" (Контрреволюционные преступления).

Article 58-1 is aimed at the overthrow and subversion or weakening of the government elected by the workers' and peasants' councils, the government of the Soviet Union, union and autonomous republics elected on the basis of the Constitution of the Soviet Union and the constitutions of the Soviet Union. union republics economic, political and any actions aimed at undermining or weakening their achievements in the national sphere are called counter-revolutionary.

In the concept of "counter-revolutionary crime", "counter-revolutionary" was considered a crime against the basic economic, political and national, i.e. the existing system, as well as the organs of power in the USSR of the proletarian revolution. Its analogue is currently considered a "Crime against state power" in Chapter 10 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation and is included in Chapter 29 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation as "Crimes against the constitutional system and state security". The application of Article 58-1a of the Criminal Code to high treason, that is, espionage by citizens of the USSR against the military power of the country, its state independence or inviolability, disclosure of military or state secrets, going over to the enemy's side, crossing the border is established. The highest measure of criminal punishment for such persons is confiscation of all property, self-mutilation, in a lighter case - confiscation of all property and imprisonment for up to 10 years.

According to Article 58-1b, the military personnel who committed the above crimes had all their property confiscated and were sentenced to death.

Article 58-1c provides for the confiscation of all property and imprisonment for a term of 5 to 10 years for military personnel who escaped or crossed the border, as well as adult members of their families.

At the time of the crime, the remaining adult members of the traitor's family living with them or under their guardianship will be deprived of the right to vote and exiled to remote regions for a term of 5 years.

In this we find the eternal curse of "responsibility of the families of enemies of the people." We see that this substance is applied only to the families of traitors in military service, to those who knowingly or incited treason. But this terrible substance, busy, often used as a tool of manipulation, that is, deception.

In October 1938, visiting sessions of the Military Collegium of the Supreme Court of the USSR, which conducted its work in Tashkent, acted on the basis of Article 58 of this criminal code [2].

At first, repressions were carried out in the sphere of agricultural work. Not everyone who was branded as an "enemy of the people" managed to escape punishment.

The machine of killing and repression worked tirelessly day and night. The chairman of the Arab village council of the Guzor district, Ibragim Tolaganov, was also dragged into the house. He was influenced by the fact that his father was an elder during the time of the emir, that his father Tolagan Boronov collected taxes from printers in 1918-1924, that he was against the organization of collective farms and that his father-in-law, Nor Eshon Ragimov, was a very respected and influential person. He is accused of adultery, of being denied the right to vote, of going with his youngest son Khalil to a place called Besharik (Okta city) in Afghanistan, where he works as an imam.[3.231]

How many innocent people were trapped by the red dragon of repressions by the end of 1938? A brief summary of this is yet to come. The insatiable heart devoured the sons and daughters of our country. There is no count of the victims of the Kashkadarya oasis.

The document of December 20, 1938 recorded the names of people who fell into the nets of the cruel kingdom. The evil term "enemy of the people" was still actively used and practiced. Let us note their names:

Kochkor Ataboyev worked as the head of the culture and propaganda department of the Karshi district party committee. On November 6, 1937, the Central Committee of the Uzbek Communist Party (bolsheviks) sent him to the Karshi district committee. According to him, Kochkor Ataboyev, who "conducted two major political campaigns", suffered from injustice, fell ill and did not go to work for 3 months. He was expelled from the ranks of the All-Union Communist Party (bolsheviks) for refusing to work for the party. Kirill Vasilyevich Shvirev was anti-party and hid his social affiliation. For these reasons, the label "enemy of the people" was printed.

Adolat Rasulova - her husband, an enemy of the people, hid Rasulova's hostile activities, his imprisonment in the party organization was not reported. Rasulov was expelled from the party.

Among the victims of the 1938 repressions, Mikhail Gavrilovich Konoplenka, Meiliboy Yerbo'tayev, Gulamhasan Talib ogle Gasanzoda, Grigory Stepanovich Khachaturyan, Inoyat Kudratov, Sergei Bykov, Nikita Timonin, Gulomdzhon Usmanov will also be mentioned. All of them were imprisoned as enemies of the people.

Needless to say, how the fate of those who were imprisoned under the curse of the "enemy of the people" was decided, they were almost never left alive.

In October 1917, V. I. Lenin, who was the leader of the coup d'etat in Russia and whose slogan formed the basis of the rule of the Red Kingdom, addressed the cruel Bolshevik forces: "Be cruel enough to be an example, be stupid, without asking anyone "Let them shoot, not allowing riots," he taught. [page 3.234]

The words of the writer and historian Igor Bunich are appropriate here: "The Bolsheviks were the first in the world to subject their people to mass extermination in a new way. This allowed a handful of scoundrels to remain in power." [4;10] The USSR government, which ruled for about 74 years, in the 20th century the massacre committed by the Nazis of Germany and Hitler, the genius of the

Germans, was committed against entire nations, and aggression against its own people was associated with Stalin, named Lenin. By the end of 1935, the Soviet Union began to tighten its policy of persecution and repression against socially alien elements. It was required that localities provide a list of socially alien elements. This meant that the previous period of increased repression was just beginning.

In his "secret" letter to the secretary of the district party committee, Saidkhanov, G. Ya. Veide criticizes the fact that the list of foreign elements from the Behbudin district is insufficient. Veide explains the shortage of people by 5 kulaks, 30 priests, 61 merchants, 15 emir officials. It is noted that most of them are not included in the list and are still wanted.

The document presented to the Kashkadarya district party committee on September 4, 1935, is called the indicator "Number of socially alien elements". It provides the following information [3;377]:

Districts	kulaks	priests	merchants	Emir officials
Behbudi	5	30	61	15
Koson	37	69	-	45
Chirokchi	159	38	42	12
Guzor	112	30	35	6
Yakkabog	95	64	53	53
Shakhrisabz	59	21	24	8
Kitob	144	86	-	-
Beshkent	64	24	28	-
Dekhkonoobod	27	21	4	4
Total:	702	383	247	143

It seems that the Soviet state did not stop using disgusting methods to create fear in people in order to carry out its policy. The policy of repression was not enough to wipe out many families, but it was able to create enough fear in people for a hundred years.

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